

Panchromatic observations of X-ray binaries

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Accretion is the natural process by which objects in the universe grow in mass. As a consequence of the angular momentum typically carried by the accreted material, during this process, the material tends to organise itself in the form of a thin disc.

Disc winds and jets are ubiquitous among accreting systems on all scales, from active galactic nuclei down to young stellar objects. Thus, mass loss appears to be a universal – and perhaps necessary – part of the accretion process. These outflows can carry large amounts of mass and energy, representing a key mechanism by which these systems interact with their environment (“feedback”). They may also be responsible for the mysterious state changes observed in low-mass X-ray binaries (LMXBs; [1]).

Transient LMXBs harbouring black holes and neutron stars provide us arguably with one of the best laboratories for studying the interplay between accretion, jets and disc winds. While spending most of their time in quiescence, these systems undergo violent outbursts, during which they brighten dramatically across the whole electromagnetic spectrum. These outbursts typically last hundreds of days and reflect a sudden increase in the accretion rate onto the compact object. Over the course of an outburst, LMXBs exhibit two distinct spectral states. In quiescence and on the rise, the X-ray spectrum is dominated by a hard power law component. By contrast, near the peak of the eruption and during the early decline, most of the accretion luminosity emerges in a soft, thermal component. These spectral states are thought to be a consequence of different accretion geometries close to the central object. Specifically, the hard state is associated with a hot, optically thin, geometrically thick accretion flow, which is largely replaced by an optically thick, geometrically thin accretion disc in the soft state.

Intriguingly, a strong connection between these two spectral states and two distinct types of outflows is observed. In the hard state, steady compact radio jets are seen. On the other hand, during the soft state, blue-shifted absorption lines associated with highly ionised accretion disc winds are often observed. This anti-correlation between winds and jets in the different spectral states is poorly understood. One possibility is that both outflows are magnetically driven, but this would require a dramatic reconfiguration of the global magnetic field. On the other hand, the strong irradiation of the disc provides a natural explanation if the winds are thermally driven. Remarkably, blue-shifted absorption lines have recently also been discovered in optical and NIR recombination lines. These features must also be produced in an outflow, but the physical conditions traced by these outflows are different. Despite this, the characteristic Doppler velocities of all types of wind signatures are

comparable, even though they have never been observed simultaneously.

While monochromatic observations can provide important insights of particular regions in the systems, multi-wavelength (MW) observations are required to develop a comprehensive physical picture. Coordinated observations across observatories at different wavelengths and resolutions have already provided groundbreaking insights into the physics of these accretion discs and their outflows. Examples include the determination of the magnetic field and location of the jet [2], its geometry and energetics [3] and evolution throughout an outburst [4], as well as how the dense winds can contribute to the transport of angular momentum, irradiation of the disc and how this affects their appearance and outburst evolution [5].

In this contribution, I present an overview of a MW campaign I have led which succeeded in obtaining simultaneous time-resolved observations of an erupting LMXB (*Swift J1858*) across the electromagnetic spectrum. This remarkable data set has already yielded the first detection of *ultraviolet* wind signatures in an transient LMXB [6], but there is much more yet to come.

Campaign overview

In Figure 1, I present an overview of the time-resolved simultaneous observations we obtained over a 4-hour window while *Swift J1858* was in its luminous hard state. The characteristic flaring of the source across all wavelengths is thought to be consequence of accretion taking place at super-Eddington rates. It is immediately obvious that the amplitude of the variations is increasing toward shorter wavelengths. Moreover, the absence of lags between different bands points to the X-ray emitting region as the driver of the strong variability.

The near-IR band exhibit strong short “bursts” on timescales of seconds on top of the normal flaring activity. The irregular morphology of these bursts indicate a non-thermal origin. However, there is no counterpart to these rapid variations at higher energies. The variable radio emission is likely driven by variations in the accretion flow being propagated to the compact jet. The lower panel shows the integrated flux of the Bowen blend + He II ($\lambda 4686$; B+He: this line complex can be interpreted as a proxy to the inaccessible extreme ultraviolet). In the same panel I also plot the significance with which wind signatures are detected (or not) in the $H\alpha$ line (triangles). While the B+He follows the overall flaring variability, the wind signatures seems to be anti-correlated with it. More specifically, the wind is most clearly detected when the source is faintest (clearly illustrated during the first hour of the campaign). This could be interpreted as the wind signatures becoming undetectable as the outflow becomes over-ionised by the extreme radiation field.

References

- [1] Shields, G. A., et al. 1986, ApJ 306, 90
 [2] Gandhi, P., et al. 2010 MNRAS, 407, 2166
 [3] Tetarenko, A. J., et al. 2021, MNRAS, 504, 3862
 [4] Russell, T. D., et al. 2020 MNRAS, 498, 5772.
 [5] Tetarenko, B. E., et al. 2020, MNRAS, 495, 3666
 [6] Castro Segura, N., et al. 2021, *subm.*

Figure 1: Overview of the strictly simultaneous data collected during the campaign. Instruments were sorted from top to bottom with increasing wavelength, in the X-rays *NICER* and *NuSTAR*, *HST* in the UV, *Liverpool Telescope* in the optical, *VLT/HAWK-I* in the near-IR and *VLA* (4.5 + 7.5 GHz bands) in radio. Finally, in the bottom panel the flux of the Bowen blend and the optical He II as measured from the *VLT/X-Shooter* spectra is shown with green dots. The dark (GTC/OSIRIS) and light (*VLT/X-Shooter*) triangles in the same panel indicate the significance of the wind signatures (right axis) and the horizontal dashed line indicate the 3σ level.

Short CV

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